

There are three species of bear native to North America. Most numerous North American bears. The most common is the American black bear, followed by the brown bear and then the polar bear. Discovered throughout Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Weighs 200 to 600 pounds. Can be darkish or gentle brown (cinnamon), typically even white. Not all the time black in coloration. 900,000 and not threatened. □□ Location: The American black bear might be discovered all through Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Nevertheless, some subspecies such as the Louisiana black bear are protected below the U.S. □□ Dimension: Adults weigh 200 to 600 pounds and are 5 to 6 ft in size. □□ Options: Most black bears are black, but their fur can range from darkish brown to lighter brown (cinnamon) and even white on uncommon occasions. They have pointed ears and a straight face. Of all of the bear species black bears are some of one of the best at climbing bushes. Their relatively smaller measurement and shorter claws make them fast and nimble to climb timber for safety, food, and even hibernation. Nearly all of their diet is vegetarian consisting of berries, plant shoots, and nuts. □□ Food plan: Their diversified diet offers them the flexibility to reside in a big range of habitats. In addition they eat insects, fish, and carrion. □□ Harmful? They're the most definitely bear to be encountered in the backcountry. And sure, they love honey. The grizzly and Kodiak are the two subspecies of brown bears in North America. Most widespread bear species are discovered within the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Center East. Brown bears are the most widespread of all bear species, found within the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Middle East. Grizzlies are accountable for almost all bear assaults in North America, with 46 per 12 months. Though their conservation status is "least concern", their unfold-out nature and decreased habitat make most of the small remaining pockets fragile. The 200,000 brown bears of the world occupy a wide variety of habitats spanning deserts, forests, and mountains. All brown bears share a large build, a dish-shaped face, and a shoulder hump. Their hair is lighter at the ideas, which led to the title of the most famous subspecies, grizzly. Brown bears forage on roots, berries, insects, and fish, and a few even hunt young mammals such as elk and moose. Their colour varies from gentle blonde to dark brown. The 2 subspecies in North America are the grizzly and Kodiak. □□ Location: Grizzly bears are found within the northern USA, Canada, and Alaska. □□ Measurement: Adults weigh 400 to 790 pounds, are 6.5 feet long, and have a shoulder peak of 3.3 toes. □□ Weight-reduction plan: Grizzlies eat berries, nuts, salmon and have been identified to prey on large mammals. Coastal grizzlies tend to be bigger than these found in the Rocky Mountains on account of a richer food regimen. Each year there are forty six attacks and 6 deaths. □□ Dangerous? Identified for his or her aggressive habits, grizzlies are accountable for the most bear assaults in North America. □□ Location: Kodiak bears are solely discovered on the Kodiak Islands, an archipelago in southwestern Alaska. □□ Size: Kodiak bears are almost as massive as polar bears, weighing 600 to 1,400 pounds, eight toes long, and four toes tall on the shoulder. □□ Diet: Their eating regimen is just like mainland grizzly bears. Nonetheless, on account of extra plentiful food sources, the islands can assist a denser bear population. Geographic isolation from the mainland allowed the 3,500 Kodiak bears to grow to be their very own subspecies. This has led to a more complex social construction which leads to less battle between bears. □□ Dangerous? Like grizzlies, Kodiak bears could be aggressive. Resulting from their isolation, there is only one attack on people every other yr. Largest species of bear on the earth weighing between 800 and 1,300 pounds. Food regimen is mostly made up of meat, typically from seals. □□ Location: Polar bears are the biggest bears and largest land carnivores on the planet. Fur appears white however is actually clear. The world's 20,000 to 30,000 polar bears vary in the snow-lined arctic ice in Alaska, Canada, Russia, and Norway. □□ Dimension: Adult polar bears are 800 to 1,300 pounds and can be 7 to 10 feet tall. They are a threatened species attributable to loss of habitat from local weather change. Despite their enormous size polar bears could be fast, maintaining a 6 mph tempo in the water. □□ Options: Compared to different bears, polar bears have a slimmer body, narrow head, longer neck, and paddle-like paws. For context, swimmer Michael Phelps received Olympic gold medals with a 4.7 mph tempo! □□ Food regimen: Their food regimen consists mostly of animals, particularly seals which they can odor from a mile away. Though they seem white, their fur is definitely clear and their skin is black. □□ Harmful? Polar bears could be extremely dangerous. They see people as potential prey. Assaults are uncommon because of the remote nature of their habitat. Recognized for its cream shade chest blazes. At 300 pounds one of the smaller bears. Easy to tame and sometimes common in circuses. □□ Location: The Asian black bear is present in forests and shrublands throughout Asia from Iran to Japan. The inhabitants is estimated at 40,000 to 50,000 and is taken into account vulnerable. □□ Measurement: One of many smaller species, adults weigh round 300 pounds and stand 47 to seventy five inches tall. □□ Weight loss plan: Depending on the season it generally feeds on small mammals, birds, fish, mollusks and carcasses or grasses, fruits, berries, seeds, insects, and honey. Assaults on humans are rising as people encroach

on their habitat. □□ Dangerous? They are one in all the simplest bears to tame (and due to this fact common in circuses), but Asian black bears are more aggressive than their North American counterparts. Found solely in China. 99% of its weight-reduction plan is bamboo. In truth, the second particular person in history to receive a facial transplant was mauled by an Asian black bear while defending his sheep. Identified for its iconic white face, eye patches, and striped physique. □□ Location: Pandas are discovered solely in China. Solely 1,500 to 2,000 remain in the wild and they're considered a susceptible species. □□ Size: Pandas weigh round 300 pounds and will be over four toes tall, an impressive feat contemplating they weigh solely about 3.5 ounces at birth. It also has a close cousin, the Qinling panda which has the same sample in gentle brown and white. □□ Weight loss plan: Not like other bears the panda's food regimen is homogeneous; 99% of what they eat is bamboo. □□ Options: The enormous panda is iconic for its white face, black eye patches, and striped body. All that fibrous bamboo keeps them common: they poop over 40 instances a day! □□ Harmful? Attacks are rare however harmful, provided that pandas have certainly one of the highest chew forces of any carnivore. Smallest Bear weighing fifty five to 143 pounds. Present in South East Asia. 8 to 10-inch lengthy tongue for slurping up insects and honey. □□ Location: The Sun bear is discovered in the forest and shrubland of South East Asia and India. It is the least studied bear and. Its population is uncertain but considered weak and on the decline due to loss of habitat and poaching. Solar bears are hunted for their gallbladders and different physique elements used in conventional medicines. □□ Size: They stand solely 39 to 55 inches and weigh 55 to 143 pounds making them the smallest bear. □□ Features: Sun bears have strongly curved claws, small rounded ears, and a short snout. They are named for his or her pale, horseshoe-formed chest patch that looks like a rising sun. Additionally they eat seeds, fruit, birds, and deer. □□ Diet: Solar bears tear apart trees and nests to eat ants, bees, beetles, termites, and honey. Their love of honey has given them the nickname "honey bears." In actual fact, they have an incredibly long tongue (8-10 inches) for slurping up insects and honey. Native to South Asia. □□ Harmful? Because of its shy nature, assaults are rare. Lengthy, shaggy fur and mane gave them the name sloth bear. Sloth bears are feared by rhinos and elephants. □□ Location: The Sloth bear is found within the low elevation savanna and shrubland of India, Nepal, and Sri Lanka. With a declining population of less than 20,000, they're thought of susceptible. □□ Size: They are 55 to 75 inches lengthy and weigh 200 to 300 pounds. □□ Options: With their long shaggy fur and mane, they are easy to inform aside from other Asiatic bears. In actuality, they're very fast and can out-gallop humans. European explorers mistook them for sloths after seeing them hanging upside down from bushes. They are noisy, messy eaters tearing up termite mounds with their big curved claws. □□ Weight-reduction plan: Their food regimen consists of termites, ants, and fruit. □□ Dangerous? They are one of the crucial aggressive bears, with the most assaults on humans, principally as a result of surprise encounters. They blow the dust round with large puffs and suck the ants up so loudly they are often heard 600 ft away. Sloth bears stand their floor if threatened and don't combine well with rhinos and elephants, usually charging at one another when in proximity. Solely South American bear. World's last quick-confronted bear. The identify "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings around their eyes that seem like glasses. This vulnerable species of 13,000 to 18,000 remaining bears are found within the cloud forests of the Andes from Argentina to Ecuador. □□ Size: They are mid-sized, weighing 175 to 275 pounds, and standing 47 to seventy nine inches tall. □□ Location: The spectacled bear is the world's last short-faced bear and the one bear native to South America. □□ Features: The title "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings around their eyes that sometimes seem like glasses. They spend most of their time in timber where they construct nest platforms, sleep and jealously guard treasured fruit and carcasses. □□ Food regimen: Spectacled bears are mostly herbivores with a weight loss plan consisting of principally cactus, bromeliad, palm hearts, and fruit, but they will opportunistically eat mammals like rabbits and tapirs. □□ Dangerous? Dwelling in distant mountains, these shy bears could be the least harmful of all bear species. Their our bodies are smaller than polar bears however bigger than grizzlies. The Grolar bear (aka Pizzly) is a uncommon hybrid of a polar bear and a grizzly bear that occurs in each nature and captivity. Grolar bear behavior is closer to the polar bear. They characteristic the lengthy necks of polar bears and the shoulder humps of grizzlies. In captivity, they have been documented stomping toys, much like how polar bears break ice. Black-brown hybrid bears have been bred in captivity, notably at the London Zoo in 1859, but haven't been confirmed in the wild. In 1986, a suspected grizzly-brown hybrid was shot however DNA checks had been unable to determine what kind of bear it was. Adorable koalas should not bears, they're burly marsupials. Water bears aren't bears either, they're indestructible, microscopic animals that can survive in space. Most bear assaults occur when a bear is startled or protecting their cubs. Crimson pandas? They're in their own household which might be closer cousins with skunks and raccoons than bears. 1. BEWARE OF YOUR SURROUNDINGS. Look ahead to bear

scat and bear tracks that may point out a bear is close by, during which case you need to be further vigilant. Listed below are a number of suggestions you should use to forestall bear encounters and keep you and your hiking buddies secure.

2. **MAKE NOISE.** This helps bears know you're here so they don't unintentionally startle them. Consider attaching a bear bell to your pack.
3. **KEEP YOUR DISTANCE.** While you may have nice intentions, a bear is prone to really feel threatened when it sees you approaching and defend itself.
3. **Secure YOUR SCENTED Gadgets (AT CAMP).** Should you see a bear, do not attempt to approach or feed it. This consists of meals, but also your toiletries, for instance. Whichever method you choose, be certain that it is a minimum of 200 toes away from your tent so you do not entice bears to your campsite.
4. **Stay CALM.** If you happen to meet a bear, do not run. Try to make your self look as big as attainable, waving your arms above your head. It's also possible to prolong a jacket above your head to make yourself look bigger. Lock this stuff in a bear canister or use a bear bag to hold them up in a tree. Do not scream or try to scare the bear.
5. **USE BEAR SPRAY (AS A last RESORT).** Converse to it calmly and slowly back away. Full instruction on how to make use of bear spray right here. If the bear is dangerously shut (30 toes) or is charging at you, pull out your bear spray and use it in 1-2 second bursts, aiming slightly downward.
6. **Combat Again.** If all else fails and a bear attacks you, don't play dead. Which bear is the biggest? Averaging 900-1500 lbs, 8.0 to 8.4 ft long, and 4.0 to 5.25 toes tall, the largest bear by each size and weight is the polar bear. The most important ever recorded was 2,200 lbs. Fight back with all of your power and hope that it'll back down. Which bear is probably the most dangerous? All bears are harmful if provoked. Globally, the Asian black bear is known for probably the most attacks. When in bear country, it's always smart to hold bear spray. It's well deserved, especially when cubs are round. Annually there are roughly 46 grizzly attacks, 6 resulting in loss of life. In North America, grizzly bears have the most fearsome popularity. Which bear is the strongest? Whereas you're most more likely to see an American black bear, on average there is just one attack per 12 months. By way of uncooked chunk power, measured in Newtons, the polar bear's bite reigns supreme. All bears are sturdy and not to be messed with. When utilizing the bite pressure quotient (chunk power relative to dimension), the solar bear packs the most punch. Originally named "Hotfoot Teddy", Smokey Bear was a black bear cub discovered within the spring of 1950 after a wildfire in New Mexico. He had climbed a tree to flee the hearth however sustained burns on his paws and hind legs. Soon after he turned an icon and to this present day is the star of the longest-operating public service announcement marketing campaign. Yogi Bear is an animated bear known for his love of "pic-a-nic" baskets. Extra importantly Yogi Bear has inspired numerous via-hikers to attempt to grasp the artwork of "yogi-ing", the act of not quite begging but receiving favors from strangers. Baloo a sloth bear, although he has some traits of the Asian black bear. He's an easygoing, pleasant bear who lives a accountability-free way of life. He also is likely to be the first bear to obtain his pilot's license. Before he was the storybook teddy bear, Winnie the Pooh was a black bear from Canada which the author's son typically would visit on the London Zoo. Winnie is short for "Winnipeg," the town in Canada near where he was from. Chris also wrote How to Hike the Appalachian Path. Equal parts backpacking meals and ultralight gear. After through-hiking the Appalachian Path, Chris Cage created Greenbelly to provide quick, filling and balanced meals to backpackers. Get epic ideas, guides and how-to's in your inbox each two weeks.

